

**SERMON OF PETRO MOHYLA «THE CROSS OF CHRIST THE SAVIOR AND EVERYONE» IN
THE PSYCHOLINGUISTIC DIMENSION**

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Abstract

The purpose of the article is to examine the sermon of Petro Mohyla «The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone» as a communicative phenomenon in the Ukrainian religious discourse of the seventeenth century. Considering sender and addressable component, the communicative guideline, the structure of the text and the expressive means used by the preacher, the peculiarities of psychological perception, understanding and listening to the text of the sermon are taken into account.

The fundament of the theoretical base of the research is the general scientific methods of analysis, synthesis, systematization, generalization. In the course of the research, a discursive method was used, which included the analysis of the sermon, taking into account the peculiarities of religious communication, principles of interactivity and dialogue, socio-cultural context.

The specificity of the addressability and addressable and realization of the speech influence of the preacher in the narration is analyzed. The specific manifestation of the phenomenon under investigation is the use of the old Ukrainian language during the proclamation of the sermon, although the dominant at that time was the position on the clearly defined sphere of application of the Church Slavonic language in religious texts. It is revealed that the content of the text of the sermon is determined by the needs of the believers, which satisfies the preacher, with the need to influence not only upon the intellect, but also the emotions, wishes and feelings of the listening audience.

Features of the internal and external structure of the sermon are characterized. The article deals with the artistic and stylistic peculiarities of sermon due to the general nature of the oratorical-preaching genre as a speech activity aimed at recipients, which involves interactivity, dialogue and functionality in the use of expressive means for the purpose of influencing the listeners.

Keywords: Petro Mohyla, sermon «The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone», psycholinguistic analysis, communication, religious discourse.

Introduction Modern linguistics is not limited only by studying of a language, but is based on the analysis of speech activity, which joins the explanation of general aspects of human cognition, becomes one of the important tools for studying mental and cognitive processes of the human psyche. In this case it is obvious to talk about the emergence of a new interdisciplinary science – psycholinguistics. In addition to the above, psycholinguistics increasingly focuses on the problems of communication, social interaction in various spheres of human existence, because communication is an essential type of realization of human existence in various dimensions of his life, including in the spiritual and religious aspect.

The relevance of the proposed study is due to the lack of research in the scientific literature devoted to the study of psycholinguistic and communicative dimensions of Petro Mohyla's sermon " The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone ", which is considered a new stage in the development of Old Ukrainian preaching discourse. Communicativeness of speech is determined by the general nature of the oratorical-preaching genre as a speech activity aimed at recipients, which involves interactivity, dialogue, functionality in the use of expressive means to influence listeners.

The need for psycholinguistic analysis of the text of the sermon is due to the fact that the utterance and perception of the sermon is a thought-speaking process that has the status of a linguistic-cultural phenomenon and special mental activity of the subject and object of

the sermon. Language, verbalizing various concepts, reflects the complex processes of cognitive activity, reflects the state, emotional experiences, mood of the preacher and listeners of the sermon. A specific manifestation of the phenomenon under study is the use of the Old Ukrainian language (instead of Church Slavonic) during the sermon, which was carried out in order to make the sermon more accessible to listeners.

Studying the processes of preaching and perception of speech by listeners, we rely in our research on the ideas expressed in the psycholinguistic works of O. Leontiev (Leontiev, 2003), S. Zasekina, L. Zasekina, (Zasekina, 2008; Zasekina & Zasekin, 2002), L. Kalmykova (Kalmykova, 2008); S. Kuranova (Kuranova, 2012).

We can state that in modern psycholinguistic research the communicative-cognitive potential of religious discourse, psycholinguistic interpretation of certain religious concepts have become more active. Unfortunately, there are no psycholinguistic studies that analyze sermon as a special genre of religious discourse - as a speech activity of a spiritual and religious nature, which is considered as an act of communication, because speech has a communicative function and is a means of communicative activity. Until now, there has been no holistic psycholinguistic study of Petro Mohyla's sermon " The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone " as a communicative phenomenon within the framework of the old Ukrainian preaching discourse of the 17th century.

The aim of the article is to try to make a psycholinguistic analysis of the sermon "The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone" as a communicative phenomenon in the Ukrainian religious discourse of the XVII century, given the addressee component, communicative instruction, understanding and interpretation by the listeners of the text of the sermon.

The main objectives of the article we consider: 1) theoretical analysis of the internal structure and external structural organization of the sermon "The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone" as a communicative phenomenon in the religious discourse of the XVII century; 2) empirical study of the specifics and nature of the means of expression used by the addressee of the sermon in order to have a psychological impact on the addressee; 3) outlining the future prospects of studying the text of the sermon - the study of semantic and functional features of lexical antonymy and synonymy, which is used to enhance the emotional impact on listeners.

Aims, tasks

The fundamental base of the theoretical background of the study are general scientific methods of analysis, synthesis, systematization, generalization. In the article a descriptive method that combines the methods of observation, comparison, interpretation and classification of theoretical research material is used. Usage of the cultural-historical method of content and structure of the sermon, helps us to understand peculiarities in the context of the Ukrainian baroque culture of the XVII century. The hermeneutic method (analysis and interpretation of the sermon text) was used to reveal the communicative parameters of the sermon. In the course of the research a discursive method was used, which provides for the analysis of the sermon taking into account the peculiarities of religious communication, the principles of interactivity and dialogue, socio-cultural context.

Results and Discussion

Sermon (term used by I. Ogienko) is one of the types of oratory and preaching art, which in its content is instructive and educational. The purpose of preaching is to convey the meaning of God's word to the minds of men. "Accordingly, we consider preaching discourse as such a meaningful activity that is realized in the communication of the religious community of people and aimed at understanding, interpreting and mastering the postulates of faith," – notes researcher Y. Oleshko (Oleshko 2017, p. 33).

The main task of the preacher was to engage the audience in the foundations of the Christian faith, to evoke feelings of gratitude to God, to encourage the audience to be patient in the name of the afterlife. Researcher F. Batsevych believes that the sermon is a speech act of the directive type, because it aims to persuade the addressee to certain actions, to use its content and basic guidelines in practical life (Batsevych 2005, p. 23).

The sermon is dedicated to Prince Jeremiah Vyshnevetsky, who recently returned from abroad. Petro Mohyla persuades him to imitate his ancestors who held the Orthodox faith. It seems that, in composing the text of the sermon, the author selected an extremely rich

and informative material in order for his sermon to be an appropriate place and time of utterance, as well as the expectations of the listeners. The sermon has a clear compositional structure and is a complete integrity.

It consists of two large parts, which are logically complete blocks, closely related in content. The text is clearly structured, each of the parts has the appropriate semantic and linguistic content. The chosen theme is revealed in both parts of the sermon.

Already at the beginning of the sermon (Mog., Kr 1914, p. 267) the problem is formulated and the attitude to the original interpretation of the author of his speech, who compares Christ as a God-man and an ordinary person and uses the word "cross" in a literal and figurative sense. The main idea of the title is gradually unfolded and embodied in the text of the sermon, in which the preacher reflects on the symbolic meaning of the cross carried by the Son of God and the cross as the destiny of each person, reflecting the originality of the sermon with its atypical title.

At the beginning of Petro Mohyla's sermon "The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone" there is an epigraph, with which the preacher expresses the main idea of the sermon - a quote translated from the Holy Scriptures indicating where the fragment comes from. The author acquaints the listeners with the structure of the sermon, says that it will consist of two parts, which will reveal the chosen topic. In the introduction, the preacher briefly talks about the content of each of these parts, separating them with ordinal numbers. Then the preacher points to the theme of the sermon, explains and clarifies the term "theme" borrowed from the Greek language, using the word "foundation": Gema, that is, the foundation of the sermon... (Mog., Kr . 1914, p. 392). The presence of this gloss indicates that the term "topic" was new to the listeners of that time and therefore required explanation.

Thus, in the structure of the preface to the sermon there are the following elements: epigraph; the translation of the Gospel story, which led to the choice of theme; segment of addressing listeners and saints. The task of the introduction was to determine the purpose of the sermon, to acquaint the audience with the range of issues to be addressed, and to prepare the audience for the attentive perception of the preacher's words.

The largest in the sermon is the narrative part, in which the leading theme is Christ as a model of patience. In the first part of the narrative, the author explains why Christians honor the image of the cross and what the figure of the cross means in Christianity. In the second part, P. Mohyla interprets the words from the Gospel, expressed by Jesus Christ: Whoever wants to follow me, let him restrain himself, and let him take up his cross, and let him follow me (Mog., Kr. 1914, p. 405). The preacher reflected on the symbolic significance of the cross carried by the Son of God and on the cross of each person and his freedom of will. In this work, the author argues that without patience, without understanding the need to carry his cross, man can not achieve salvation.

Analyzing Christ's call to follow him, the thinker emphasized that the Savior did not force anyone to follow him, but wanted everyone who believed in him to

choose the way of the cross of patience consciously and voluntarily (Nichik 1997, p. 30). Petro Mohyla's sermon "The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone" is full of a deep philosophical understanding of human life. The Metropolitan instructs the listeners: carrying his cross presupposes the renunciation of the temptations and vanities of the world, because, in his opinion, they hinder the spiritual transformation of man (Nichik 1997, p. 31).

To meet the spiritual aspirations and aesthetic needs of a particular recipient, to achieve constant contact with listeners, especially psychological, the author uses a dialogical form of sermon.

However, according to the rules of the genre, sermons are a type of religious communication where the verbal position of one side of communication is actively expressed. The peculiarity of communication during the sermon is the silence of the addressee, but the speaker must ensure its two-sidedness, - notes the Polish researcher (Bizior 2006, p. 47).

Despite the fact that sermons in the way of interaction between communicators are monologue speech, sermons are characterized by internal (immanent) dialogue, which reflects the understanding of the presence of another participant in communication, which gives meaning to this process. Dialogicity requires an active position and reaction of both communicators, despite the fact that the verbalization of the presence of one of them is limited in relation to the preaching discourse. (Oleshko 2017, p. 14)

Researcher G. Chuba claims that dialogue is a form of communicative communication close to the linguistic experience of an ordinary listener, which is often used in everyday situations - it resembled an ordinary conversation. This way of presenting the material helped to bring the addressee closer to the preacher. Dialogue makes it possible to level the higher position of the speaker in relation to the recipients, to create the effect of two-way communication. The most important thing in preaching discourse is the feeling and awareness of the dialogic nature of speech. At the same time, the dialogical form of the organization of the sermon remains subordinated to the author's monologue - the main organizational structure of the sermon (Chuba 2003, p. 144).

Preaching requires a preacher not only to be an ardent speaker, to be able to clearly set and understand their goals and desires, to have the ability to focus their thoughts, express their feelings and share thoughts, but also to be able to impress, capture the listener's attention, to be a psychologist, to understand the needs and features of the audience. Petro Mohyla's sermon was addressed to parishioners who gathered in the church, as indicated by the phrases he uses: Orthodox Christians (Mog., Kr. 1914, p. 392, p. 405).

Since there were many simple, "common people" among the Orthodox listeners who came to pray, we see in Mohyla's sermon the desire to make the sermon accessible to all. That is why in the sermon "The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone" almost all the texts of the Holy Scriptures were written in Ukrainian (Nichyk 1997, p. 89), although the dominant position at that time was on the clearly defined scope of Church

Slavonic in religious texts. The thinker did all this in order to bring the Holy Scriptures closer to ordinary listeners, because there were certain difficulties in perceiving and understanding the liturgical services.

Petro Mohyla emphasized that the language of the people is given by God, and conducting sermons in a foreign language is a mockery of believers. According to Christ's commandments, there are no obstacles to the use of the native language in the Ukrainian church and liturgical life. Thus, the Epistle of the Apostle Paul to the Corinthians says: "How many, for example, there are different languages in the world - and none of them is insignificant! ... when I pray in a foreign language, my spirit prays, but my mind is unfruitful! ... But in the Church I prefer to say five understandable words to teach others than ten thousand words in a foreign language!" (I Cor.: 14, p.10-19). The sermons in Ukrainian gathered many believers.

During the sermon, much attention is paid to the problem of truthfulness, truthfulness of the statements, the need for a thorough explanation, because the audience not only listened to the proposed sermon, but also had to use its content in practice.

In Petro Mohyla's sermon "The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone" there are dialogues of a polemical nature. But in contrast to polemical literature, the dialogue in the sermon does not always end with a solution to a particular problem, but rather only describes, highlights it. For example, in the first part of the sermon, the author explains the meaning of the symbol of the cross in Christianity and justifies the need for Christians to overshadow themselves with the sign of the cross. But opponents did not recognize the sanctity of the symbol of the cross and did not see the need to impose the sign of the cross. The preacher gives possible excuses for imaginary opponents, and then refutes them, arguing his opinion with numerous proofs he found in the biblical texts.

The most important thing in preaching discourse is the feeling and awareness of the dialogic nature of speech. The author uses the traditional method of preaching dialogism in order to activate the mental activity and attention of listeners with a number of questions and answers, to involve them in joint (preacher and believers) "co-creation" of the sermon, to influence the way of thinking and behavior of the listener. Interrogative pronouns and adverbs were one of the main grammatical means of sentence designed in the dialogue, and some of them still function in the Ukrainian language.

A significant number of questions in the text under study concern the understanding and interpretation of the meaning of certain provisions of the Holy Scriptures and the texts of the Church Fathers.

The rhetorical questions attested in the text of the sermon. S. Balli interprets not just as a question, but as an indirect expressive language, built on the expressiveness of the voice (Balli 1955, p. 38), which enhanced the pathos of speech and served to implement the moralistic and instructive content of the sermon, to ensure that students themselves come to an instructive conclusion.

The preacher tried not only to impress the listener with his knowledge of the Bible, but also to demonstrate erudition in various fields of science, in particular, in general history, ancient culture, philosophy.

Thus, although the sermon is a monologue type of speech and does not really involve the active participation of the addressee in the act of utterance, but internal dialogue is one of the important features of the linguistic organization of the structure of the sermon text.

In order to establish close contact between the preacher and the listeners, an address is used in the structure of the sermon. The designation of the addressees of the appeal is mainly on religious grounds. The addressees of the sermons are also imaginary opponents. P. Mohyla addresses in the sermon to the enemies of the Orthodox faith, who were probably not present at the time of its proclamation, but could read the sermon later. With the help of appeals, P. Mohyla expressed a negative attitude towards those who denied the basic dogmas of Orthodoxy, did not accept the worship of the cross, addressing to them.

The addressees attested in the sermon perform mainly a communicative function. The addressees of the appeals are listeners and readers, persons of the Christian cult, saints, imaginary opponents. The sermon ends with a conclusion in which the priest calls people to good thoughts and deeds.

The conclusion in the sermon is clearly structured, consists of two semantic parts, in one of which the author, summing up, emphasizes that he managed to achieve the goal arising from the topic, was set in the proposal and violated in the sermon, and pointed to the practical application of content sermons, as evidenced by the conclusion made by the preacher. In the second part of the conclusion, the author talks about the benefits of following the instructions set forth in the sermon for our souls and asks God to help make it happen.

Conclusions

Thus, the peculiarities of the internal and external structural organization of the sermon "The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone", the means of expression used by the preacher, testify to the addressee's consideration of psychological perception, understanding and interpretation of the text of the sermon, effective influence on their beliefs and values are considered. Despite the fact that the sermon on the way of interaction between communicants is a monologue speech and does not actually involve the active participation of the addressee in the act of utterance, the structure of the sermon is communicative - the sermon is characterized by internal (immanent) dialogue.

In the structure of the text of the sermon there are imaginary dialogues with the listeners in order to psychologically influence the addressee, stimulate attention and intensify the persuasive influence of the speech; polemical dialogues aimed at religious opponents and dialogues as a way of retelling biblical events. The use of dialogues served the realization of the communicative goals of the sermon and was used as a means of expression to ensure the appropriate artistic level of the sermon.

It is important to note that the focus on interactivity, dialogicity, cognition and accessibility of the sermon "The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone" for ordinary people testified to the replacement of the old Ukrainian written language by oral, vernacular.

The results of the research should be considered as a starting point in the study of psycholinguistic dimensions of the sermon "The Cross of Christ the Savior and Everyone" as a communicative phenomenon in the religious discourse of the seventeenth century. We consider promising further study of the semantic and functional features of lexical antonymy and synonymy in the structure of the sermon, which is used to enhance the emotional impact on listeners.

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